

diverse habitats around the rice field to provide harbors for various natural enemies.

References

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A generator of a web map of biological interactions for rice invertebrates

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In a rice habitat, dozens, hundreds, or even thousands of invertebrate taxa interact with each other. A complex web of biological interactions is thus generated. If we assume that 60 taxa are found in a rice habitat and they interact with each other, a total of 1,770 pathways will be generated on a web map. It is obviously impractical to draw this map by hand. However, we have not found a fast tool to generate the web map until now. For this reason, we developed a network software to automatically generate a web map of biological interactions (direct or indirect) for rice invertebrates. A web map can be drawn by a computer with investigated data or pathway information included in an html file. Fourteen distance measures can be chosen for generating pairwise taxa with significant parametric or non-parametric correlations on the basis of randomization tests

(Manly 1997, Qi and Zhang 2003, Zhang and Schoenly 2001) or classic statistical tests (Zhang and Fang 1982).

Two choices are provided to generate web pathways: (1) the first is to compute significant correlations between taxa and (2) the second is to include the pathway information in the html file.

If users choose to compile the pathway information in the html file, for instance, the following sentence should be included inside the tags <applet>...</applet>, which are a complete string of a comma-delimited list of all pairwise taxa or habitat-taxa:

```
<param name=lines value="Rice Field-Coleoptera/150,Rice Field-Diptera/150,Rice Field-Odonata/150,Rice Field-Hemiptera/150,Rice Field-Hymenoptera/150,Rice Field-Araneae/150,Rice Field-Ephemeroptera/150,Rice Field-Lepidoptera/
```

```
150,Rice Field-Cyprorida/150,Rice Field-Cyclopoida/150,Rice Field-Arthropleona/150,Rice Field-Orthoptera/150,Rice Field-Acari/150,Rice Field-Mesogastropoda/150,Rice Field-Symphyleona/150,RiceField-Thysanoptera/150,Rice Field-Blattodea/150,Coleoptera-Cyclopoida/400,Diptera-Hemiptera/400, Diptera-Cyclopoida/400, Hemiptera-Symphyleona/400,Hymenoptera-Acari/400,Arthropleona-Acari/400">
```

In this web information, "Rice Field" is the habitat name and should be linked to every taxon. The pathway lengths are 150 and 400 for different pathways.

A delimited text file should be prepared to be used by the algorithm. In this data file, the first row will be sample ID numbers and the first column will be taxon names. The values are the in-

vestigated individual numbers. Fourteen distance (or similarity) measures, including measures for continuous values—Euclidean distance, Manhattan distance, Chebyshev distance, correlation coefficient, and angular cosine; measures for multiple discrete values, linkage coefficient, co-linkage coefficients 1–3; and measures for Boolean values, point correlation coefficient, quadratic correlation coefficient, angular cosines 1–2, and Jacard coefficient—shall be available to users (Zhang and Fang 1982, Qi and Zhang 2003). The pairwise taxa with significant correlations will be calculated by the algorithm (Qi and Zhang 2003), and used to construct web information. The Pearson correlation and partial correlation will be tested with the classic t test and the other measures will be tested with randomization tests.

The software was programmed in Java Applet and HTML to enable interactive operations on the Internet and to allow easy access to users worldwide. It can be used in teaching programs and online research. Before using the software, users must have the Web browser Java enabled. Algorithm details can be found by clicking on “Hint” on the Applet window. A window will appear to show algorithm details, data file format, and references. If users have chosen to produce web information by computation, they must choose the distance measures, enter the number of taxa and the number of samples, and, if a distance measure other than the Pearson correlation or partial correlation is chosen, users must also enter the number of randomizations (e.g., 100 or 1,000) following the distance measure selected. The re-

quired statistical significance level (i.e., 0.01, which means a 99% degree of confidence) and habitat name should also be entered. Specify the data file by clicking on “Open Data File.”

A dialog box will appear, waiting for a data file to be chosen. Finally, the software can be run and the results window and web map window will be shown after the computation is finished. If an error occurs (e.g., the user forgot to enter parameter values), a warning window will appear. All these operational procedures are easy to follow (Fig. 1). In the web map window, users can drag the taxon box with the mouse to find all links to this taxon.

As an example, we use a rice invertebrate data file with 75 families and 60 samples. The automatically generated web map is shown in Figure 2.

Fig. 1. Window for input parameters.

